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Keywords:

Oshtoran Syndrome, PANS, H63D Syndrome Type-3, HFE gene, iron metabolism, micro-inflammation, neuropsychiatric issues, mitochondriopathy, organ damage, autonomic dysfunction

Of the Chairman's Desk

Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type 3) - status report

Dear Esteemed Colleagues,

I am writing to you in my capacity as Chairman of the International H63D Mutation Research Consortium to share with you some preliminary results of our ongoing research into Oshtoran syndrome (H63D syndrome type-3). As we continue our comprehensive investigation, we intend to keep the academic community informed through regular updates and reports, including this format called "Letter to the Medical Community".

Oshtoran Syndrome, also known as H63D syndrome type-3, is a multifactorial, meta-syndromic disorder characterized by a variety of clinical manifestations. These include irregular iron homeostasis, microinflammatory events, neuropsychiatric disorders, multi-organ pathologies and especially autonomic dysfunctions involving the central nervous system, the autonomic nervous system and the innate immune system. The disease is complex and requires a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to diagnosis and treatment. There is evidence that the homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D plays a role, similar to Wilson's disease, but with NTBI iron instead of copper as the causative agent. This mutation has been linked to a number of diseases, including liver disease, diabetes mellitus, pseudo-diabetes, heart disease, neurodegenerative diseases and many more symptoms.

Therefore, it is with great pleasure that I can report that our research team dedicated to learn more about all aspects of Oshtoran Syndrome has already achieved newsworthy results:

1.
We, the research team together with the board, sent out 3,000 comprehensive questionnaires, both offline and online, to clinicians worldwide across various specialties including Neurology, Endocrinology, Hematology, Immunology, Cardiology, Gastroenterology, Urology, Nephrology, and Psychiatry. The response rate exceeded our expectations. Out of the 3,000 clinicians contacted, a total of 1,268 (42.2%) responded by the deadline of November 30, 2023. Of these, only 32 were discarded due to form errors or breaches of our data protection rules. The majority of responses came from Southeast Asia, the Persian Gulf region, South Africa, North and South America. In contrast, Western Europe had a disappointing return rate of just 12.7%. For context, Indonesia had a response rate of 78.3%, and Spain the highest in Europe at 27.9%.
2.
In an initial screening of the data, 1,061 of the 1,236 usable responses (85.9%) met the preliminary diagnostic criteria for Oshtoran syndrome. Remarkably, 52.4% of patients had more than forty (>40) symptoms, a threshold that will be important for further research into Oshtoran syndrome. The rather high number of responses is extremely encouraging considering that Oshtoran syndrome is not just a rare disease, but a very rare disease. This "meta-syndrome" results from a chronic teen to adult transition of PANS syndrome combined with H63D syndrome type-1, mitochondrial cytopathy (shift to anaerobic sugar metabolism and high lactate levels) and nervous system-induced autonomic dysfunction with mild to very severe dysregulation of organs, the endocrine system and the innate immune system via nerve innervation. Genetic mutations, which we will focus on in later phases of our research, also contribute to this complexity.
3.
Autonomic dysfunction, which leads to organ dysfunction due to incorrect coordination commands via the innervation, does not only occur in the later stages of Oshtoran syndrome, when it is one of the most dangerous symptoms of the disease. Surprisingly, such symptoms, which in clinical practice appear to cause significant but less severe symptoms in the early stages, are often overlooked or misclassified in young patients. An astonishing 81.1% of patients before the age of 35 already show the first signs of autonomic dysfunction. In patients over the age of 45, this rate rises to 89.7 %, with 62.5 % then also potentially causing symptoms severe enough to be considered life-threatening. This aspect is therefore at the top of our research agenda and the first partial results will be published as soon as solid research results are available.
4.
Equally noteworthy is the rate of patients with pathologically high sympathetic tone (91.9%), elevated levels of catecholamines (95.2%), and HPA-axis disturbances (78.6%). Notably, 42.3% of patients were diagnosed with (pre-)diabetes, which, upon preliminary analysis, also correlate with exceptionally high catecholamine levels. A key focus of our future research will be to discern how many of these "diabetics" are actually suffering from pseudo-diabetes (catecholamine-induced gluconeogenesis) and might benefit from catecholamine blockers, either in place of or in addition to anti-diabetic medications. This question has also been prioritized for further investigation.

H63D Syndrome Research Consortium

We appreciate the global medical community's ongoing support and collaboration in this vital research endeavor. As we continue to unravel the complexities of Oshtoran Syndrome, we commit to sharing our findings and fostering a deeper understanding of this challenging condition.

Sincerely

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Riku Honda', written in a cursive style with a long horizontal line extending to the right.

Riku Honda
Chairman